

Studies on the Complexes of the Chlorides of Gold with Organic Sulphides.

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Philips (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 23, 257) studied the action of methyl sulphide on the chlorides of palladium, copper and gold and found that cupric chloride and auric chloride break down into the lower valency products, yielding $\text{AuCl}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ and $[\text{CuCl}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}]_2$ respectively. In the case of palladium, the author used palladium chloride and there was no further reduction. Herrmann (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2813) studied the action of dibenzylsulphide on gold chloride and obtained two compounds, $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$, named as aurodibenzyl-sulphinchloride and auric-dibenzylsulphide-dichloride respectively. The study of the above compounds shows that the organic sulphides have got a reducing action on gold chloride which latter combines with these sulphides only in the aurous state. It occurred to us whether this reduction could anyhow be prevented and whether it was possible to make gold chloride combine directly with the sulphides giving rise to the formation of compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ (R=an alkyl group).

According to the law of mass action, in the system,

the active mass of chlorine should be increased in order to minimise the decomposition of auric chloride. This was attained by the use of a mixture of nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 1 vol.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.2, 1 vol.). The reactions were all exothermic, hence they took place better when the reaction vessels were cooled in ice.

The following compounds have been prepared as a result of these reactions :

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|---|--|
| 1. (a) $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ | (b) $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ (<i>loc. cit.</i>) |
| 2. $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ | |

3. $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$
4. $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\}_2\text{S}$
5. (a) $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ (b) $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$
6. (a) $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$
- (b) $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ (*loc. cit.*)
- (c) $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ (*loc. cit.*)

The preparation of compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ in the pure state was very difficult in the case of sulphides containing a methyl or substituted methyl group, e.g., Me_2S , $\text{Me} \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{Pr}$, $(\text{Ph} \cdot \text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$; for these have got a great tendency to form aurous compounds very readily, so that they are generated simultaneously during the preparation of the former; compounds of both types having very nearly similar solubility could not be separated from one another by fractional crystallisation. If in these cases the product be kept in contact with dilute aqua regia for several minutes, the mixture is converted into $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$. In the case of higher sulphides, e.g., diethyl, dipropyl, isobutyl sulphides etc., compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ were readily obtained while the preparation of the lower-valency products presented much difficulty.

Constitutional Formulæ.

Philips (*loc. cit.*) represented his compound, $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{Me})_2\text{S}$ by the structural formula $\text{Cl} \cdot \text{Au} : \text{S} : \text{Me}_2$ while Herrmann suggested the formulæ $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ or $\text{Au} \cdot \text{S}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{Cl}$ for the compound aurodibenzylsulphinechloride as named by him. Of these two formulæ, the first is more reasonable. The chemical reactions of compounds of this type show that the chlorine atom always remains attached to gold. They react with ammonia and pyridine, forming $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{NH}_3$ and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{Py}$. As the chlorine atom in these compounds is non-ionisable and the co-ordination number of gold in auro-compounds is 2, they can be conveniently represented by the general

Compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ are monomolecular, and nonconducting in freshly prepared acetone solution. Hence they can be represented as $\left[\begin{array}{l} \text{Cl} \\ \diagup \\ \text{Cl} \end{array} \text{Au} \begin{array}{l} \text{Cl} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{SR}_2 \end{array} \right]$, the co-ordination number being four.

The constitution of the compound $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ is somewhat interesting. This was isolated by Herrmann (*loc. cit.*) who determined its molecular weight in chloroform solution by the ebullioscopic method and found it lying between 607 and 608, instead of 482 (if the compound be monomolecular) and 964 (if the compound be dimolecular). He could not account for this anomalous result. Probably he could not prepare the compound in the pure state for its melting point is reported as 127° whereas we found it to be 133° . Determination of the molecular weight of the compound in benzene solution by the cryoscopic method gave the value at 944 corresponding to the dimolecular formula. This observation suggests two alternative formulæ, namely,

(I)

(II)

The first required the compound to be conductive and the second, to be non-conductive, and actually it was non-conductive in freshly prepared acetone solution, though the conductivity changes gradually with time due to the decomposition of the compound and other disturbing factors, thus supporting the second formula.

Potassium thiocyanate reacts in the cold with $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$, liberating the alkyl sulphide group with the formation of potassium-aurithiocyanate, but this reagent has no appreciable action on $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ in the cold. $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ was resolved by taking advantage of this reaction, keeping it in aqueous suspension and treating with potassium thiocyanate solution. The reaction took place as follows :

The products of the reaction, potassium aurithiocyanate, $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and benzylsulphide were separated from one another and obtained in the pure state (*vide* Experimental). The synthesis of the compound from $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$, as well as its resolution into these two products confirm, without doubt, the second formula suggested above.

The solution of the compound in acetone or chloroform liberates iodine from potassium iodide turning iodized starch-paper blue. This reaction indicates the presence of $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ as a component part of the compound for this latter only gives the same reaction, while $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ has got no action on iodized starch-paper.

Lastly, the constitution may be supported from another point of view. The compound Au_2Cl_4 —auroauric chloride (J. Thomson, *J. pr. Chem.*, 37, 105)—is known and its constitution definitely established as $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{AuCl}_3$. Now, since $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ forms both $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ with HAuCl_4 , it is expected that it will form $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S} \cdot \text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ —the dibenzyl sulphide compound of auroauric chloride.*

Properties.

Aurichloride dialkyl sulphides form yellow, prismatic crystals, aurochloride dialkyl sulphides are white, needle-shaped crystals, and auroaurichloride dibenzylsulphide is fine orange, silky, glistening crystals. The compounds have sharp melting points. They are soluble in most common organic solvents and are crystallisable from suitable media. They are non-conducting and monomolecular. The compounds of the type $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ react with bases like pyridine and ammonia, giving rise to the products $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{NH}_3$ (Herrmann, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2818) and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{Py}$, *i.e.*, the bases replace the sulphide molecules. The reactions are similar to the replacement of water molecule in salt-hydrates by ammonia and amines to form co-ordination compounds.

The compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ react with potassium thiocyanate and potassium thiocarbamide to form potassium auricthiocyanate and chloroauriothiocarbamide (Moir, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

*We suggest the following nomenclature for the complex gold compounds:—

$\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ —aurochloride dialkyl sulphide (*cf.* $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ —platichloride diethyl sulphide, Klason, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1499; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, ii, 67, 19; $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ —platichloride dimethyl sulphide, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 38, 359; Klason, *ibid.*, 1903, 67, 24); $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ —aurichloride dialkyl sulphide (*cf.* $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ —platichloride diethylsulphide and $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ —platichloride dipropyl sulphide, Waibak, *Z. Kryst.*, 1888, 11, 142).

$\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ —auroaurichloride dibenzyl sulphide (The name auridibenzylsulphide dichloride, as suggested by Herrmann, should therefore be rejected considering the arguments on which the constitution of the compound is based.)

1906, 103, 164), according to the following reactions.

The liberation of hydrogen chloride was detected by the action of the solution on litmus paper and also by the formation of dense white fumes of ammonium chloride with ammonia. The liberation of alkyl sulphides was detected by the characteristic odour of the respective sulphides. In the case of $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{Ph} \cdot \text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}$, the liberated dibenzylsulphide was actually isolated.

The compounds $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ are interconvertible. The former is transformed into the latter by warming with alcohol and conversely the latter is converted into the former by treatment with dilute aqua regia or chlorine water. In the case of the complexes with benzylsulphide, the transformation takes place with formation of the intermediate product auroaurichloride dibenzyl sulphide. When the white aurochloride dibenzyl sulphide is treated with dilute aqua regia, it first changes to orange and finally to yellow; again the yellow aurichloride dibenzyl sulphide, on warming with alcohol for sometime on the water-bath, first passes through the orange state, ultimately becoming perfectly white, the crystals of $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ separating. The compound, $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ has actually been synthesized from $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ by dissolving them in chloroform and crystallising from the same medium.

It may be asked whether $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ is actually a compound or a mixture of $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ in equimolecular proportions. A good amount of evidences can be put forward to prove the validity of its being a compound. When $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ are intimately mixed up, the mixture is not orange; only the yellow colour of the auric complex become lighter due to the presence of the white auro-compound the melting point of the mixture is tardy (between 115° and 120°), lower than that of either of the constituents (m. p. of $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S} = 125^\circ$, m. p. of $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S} = 118^\circ$). But when the mixture is treated with chloroform or benzene, it immediately turns orange and gradually goes into solution. When this orange compound was crystallised from chloroform, it melted sharply at 133° , $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$,

obtained directly from gold chloride and benzyl sulphide also having the same melting point. The identity of the two compounds prepared by two entirely different methods leave no reason of doubt as to the validity of its being a compound. The double molecular weight of the compound also furnishes further evidence in its support.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Formation of Aurichloride dimethyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$.

Chloroauric acid (10 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of water and 1 c.c. of the acid mixture (nitric acid, *d* 1.4, 1 vol. + hydrochloric acid, *d* 1.2, 1 vol.) was added to this solution. The solution was cooled in an ice-bath and after 10 minutes methyl sulphide (0.5 g.) dissolved in 5 c.c. of acetone was added to the solution gradually (1 c.c. at a time, at intervals of 3—5 minutes). Each time as soon as the methyl sulphide was added, there was an evolution of heat and a heavy orange liquid separated which immediately changed to an orange-yellow precipitate. Some amount of white aurochloride dimethyl sulphide appeared simultaneously. On allowing the product to remain in contact with a further quantity of the acid mixture the formation of $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ became complete.

The mixture was filtered after half an hour and washed with an acid mixture consisting of *N*/10-HCl and *N*/10-HNO₃ (1:1) and then with water and finally with alcohol. It was next dried in air and crystallised from chloroform-ether mixture from which it separated as yellow prismatic crystals, m.p. 160°. The compound was soluble in chloroform, ether, acetone, warm benzene, etc., (Found: Au, 54.11; Cl, 29.09; S, 8.28. $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 53.9; Cl, 29.13; S, 8.75 per cent.)

Formation of Aurochloride dimethyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$.

This compound was prepared by Philip's method directly from gold chloride as well as by the reduction of aurichloride methyl sulphide by warming with alcohol on the water-bath. Instead of using alcoholic or ethereal solution of aurichloride as recommended by Philip, the aqueous solution was found to give greater yield. The proportions of gold chloride and methyl sulphide used were 1:3. The substance melted at 120°. (Found: Au, 27.13; Cl, 12.08;

C, 8.12; H, 2.2. $\text{AuCl}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 66.9; Cl, 12.06; C, 8.59; H, 2.1 per cent.)

Formation of the Compound, $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$.

One gm. of $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ was warmed with 6 c.c. of pyridine on the water-bath for 15 minutes. The compound went into solution with slight decomposition, metallic gold separating out. It was next filtered, the reduced gold being removed thereby. The solution was next treated with ether when $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ was precipitated as a white crystalline precipitate. The compound was very slightly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in other common organic solvents. It melted at 250-252° with slight decomposition. (Found: Au, 63.85; Cl, 11.39; N, 4.48. $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Au, 68.24; Cl, 11.36; N, 4.49 per cent.)

Formation of Aurichloride diethyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$.

Gold chloride (8 g.) was dissolved in 2 c.c. of water, and 1 c.c. of nitric acid (*d* 1.4) was added to it. Ethyl sulphide (1.2 g.) dissolved in acetone (5 c.c.) was added to this solution. The mixture was thoroughly shaken and cooled in ice. Beautiful yellow prismatic crystals separated out of the orange heavy liquid which first separated after the addition of ethyl sulphide. These were filtered and washed with alcohol and ether and were recrystallised from dilute acetone, m.p. 95°. The properties were similar to those of the other compounds of this type. This was however found to be the most unstable compound of the series $\text{AuCl}_3\cdot\text{R}_2\text{S}$. It could be kept only two or three days after its preparation. (Found: Au, 49.78; Cl, 26.74 per cent. M. W. in benzene, 382. $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 50.06; Cl, 27.06 per cent. M. W., 398.5).

Formation of Chloroauriothiocarbamide,

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{NH}_2 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{AuCl} \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{NH} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{NH}_2 \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{NH} \end{array}$$

The substance (4.35 g.) was held in suspension in alcohol, in which the compound was slightly soluble and an alcoholic solution of thiocarbamide (1 g.) was added to it gradually. The yellow substance immediately turned orange, and gradually went into solution which was colourless. It was next allowed to evaporate in air.

Crystals of chloroaurithiocarbamide gradually separated from the solution: this was followed by the separation of unchanged thiocarbamide. The first crop was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol. This compound was also obtained from other aurichloride dialkyl sulphides. (Found: Au, 51.6; Cl, 9.2. $\text{AuClC}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires Au, 51.5; Cl, 9.28 per cent.)

Formation of Aurichloride dipropyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

Gold chloride (5 g.) dissolved in water (5 c.c.) was treated with two drops of nitric acid (d 1.4) and two drops of hydrochloric acid (d 1.2). Propyl sulphide (0.5 g.) was added to this solution at 0° , the mixture being continually teased with a glass rod. The heavy oily liquid that separated became sticky gradually, giving a granular precipitate at last. The precipitate was collected and washed with alcohol, water, and again with alcohol and ether (yield, 3 gm.).

This compound, unlike the other compounds of the series, was more soluble in ether and crystallised from the same medium. It was more stable than the ethyl sulphide compound and less sensitive to light; m.p. 80° . (Found: Au, 47.09; Cl, 25.12 per cent. M. W. in benzene, 419.1. $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 46.7; Cl, 25.27; per cent. M. W., 421.5).

Formation of Potassium aurithiocyanate from $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

Aurichloride dipropyl sulphide (4 g.) was held in suspension in 3-5 c.c. of water and potassium thiocyanate (1 g.) dissolved in 5 c.c. of water was added to it. It was next teased with a glass rod against the side of the reaction tube. The yellow salt at once turned red. The reaction was complete within 5-10 minutes. The strong smell of propyl sulphide was noticed during the reaction. It was next filtered and the precipitate dried by pressing it between the folds of a filter paper. It was next dried in air and treated with chloroform and ether to remove any unchanged aurichloride dipropyl sulphide. This compound was soluble in most common organic solvents. It decomposed at once in presence of acetone, in which it was extremely soluble. The very same compound was prepared similarly from other compounds of this series. (Found: Au, 48.2; S, 26.87; K, 8.18. $\text{KAu}(\text{SCN})_4$ requires Au, 48.1; S, 27.85; K, 8.81 per cent.)

Formation of Aurichloride isobutyl sulphide.

Gold chloride (4 g.) was dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and the solution acidified with 2 drops of nitric acid (*d* 1.4) and 2 drops of hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.2). It was next cooled and treated with isobutyl sulphide (1 c.c.). The mixture was thoroughly shaken, again cooled, and allowed to settle for fifteen minutes. The precipitate was collected and washed with alcohol (yield, about 3 g.). The compound was dried and crystallised from ether; m.p. 83°. (Found: Au, 43.86; Cl, 23.58 per cent. M. W. in benzene, 469.8. $\text{AuCl}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 43.82; Cl, 23.7 per cent. M. W., 449.5).

Formation of Aurichloride methyl-n-propyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{S} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \end{cases}$

Gold chloride (4.4 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and 1 c.c. of the acid mixture, was treated with methyl-*n*-propyl sulphide (1 c.c.). The resulting yellow precipitate was separated from the mother-liquor and washed as usual (yield, about 4 g.). The substance was crystallised from chloroform-ether; m.p. 85°. (Found: Au, 50.39; Cl, 26.66. $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{S}$ requires Au, 50.06; Cl, 27.06 per cent.).

Formation of Aurochloride methyl-n-propyl sulphide, $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{S} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \end{cases}$

Methyl-*n*-propyl sulphide (4 g.) was treated with a solution of gold chloride (4 g.), free from nitric acid, in 5 c.c. of water. A perfectly white precipitate was formed. The mixture was then cooled, filtered and washed with alcohol and ether. The substance was crystallised from alcohol. The white glistening needle-shaped crystals melted at 100-101°. (Found: Au, 61.43; Cl, 10.97. $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{S}$ requires Au, 61.1; Cl, 11.00 per cent.).

Formation of Aurichloride dibenzylsulphide, $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

Gold chloride (10 g.) dissolved in 5 c.c. of water was treated with 3 c.c. of the acid mixture. The solution was then cooled in an ice-bath and then treated with benzyl sulphide (1.5 g.) in alcoholic solution. The mixture was thoroughly shaken. Two substances, one

being yellow and the other orange, separated out. The mother-liquor was immediately decanted off and the pasty precipitate was at once treated with aqua regia (3.5 c.c.). When the whole mass became perfectly yellow, the mixture was diluted with a large excess of water, filtered and washed successively with the acid mixture, water, alcohol and ether and finally crystallised from benzene. Aurichloride dibenzyl sulphide is fairly soluble in acetone, chloroform and benzene and slightly soluble in alcohol, ether and other common organic solvents. It is very unstable in solutions, fairly stable only in the benzene medium; m.p. 118°. (Found: Au, 38.21; Cl, 31.97. $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 38.07; Cl, 32.4 per cent.)

Formation of Auroaurichloride dibenzyl sulphide, $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

This compound was prepared by the method recommended by Herrmann (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2813) by treating an ethereal solution of gold chloride (2 mol.) with an ethereal solution of benzyl sulphide (1 mol.). The compound was purified by repeated crystallisation from chloroform. The above compound had been synthesized from aurochloride dibenzyl sulphide and aurichloride dibenzyl sulphide. When these two substances were mixed in equimolecular proportions in chloroform and crystallised from the same medium, beautiful, orange, silky, prismatic crystals separated out; m.p. 133°. (Found: Au, 40.7, 40.57; Cl, 14.67, 14.57 per cent. M.W. in benzene, 944. $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 40.87; Cl, 14.73 per cent. M.W., 964).

Interaction of KSCN and $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

By this important reaction, auroaurichloride dibenzyl sulphide was resolved into its components, which elucidated the doubtful constitution of the molecular compound.

About 4 gms. of the auroauric compound in aqueous suspension were treated with 1 gm. of potassium thiocyanate in 5 c.c. of water. The mixture was then teased with a glass rod against the sides of the reaction tube. The orange colour of the substance deepened into brick red. The product was then filtered and immediately washed several times with water in order to remove unchanged potassium thiocyanate and the potassium chloride formed during the reaction. The precipitate consisting of $\text{KAu}(\text{SCN})_4$, $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ and dibenzylsulphide was dried at the ordinary temperature and extracted

several times with ether to remove dibenzylsulphide and then with chloroform to remove $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$. On concentrating the ethereal and chloroform solutions, a residue was obtained which on fractional crystallisation from chloroform and ether gave substances which on analysis were found to be pure benzylsulphide (m.p. 50°) and pure $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ (m.p. 125°). The substance left after the above treatment was pure potassium aurithiocyanate. (Found: Au, 42.42; K, 8.27. $\text{KAu}(\text{SCN})_4$ requires Au, 42.1; K, 8.33 per cent.) (Found: Au, 43.95. $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 44.12 per cent.)

Formation of Aurochloride dibenzylsulphide, $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.

The compound was prepared by Herrmann (*loc. cit.*) by warming auroaurichloride dibenzylsulphide with ethyl alcohol on the water-bath. It was found possible to prepare this compound directly from benzylsulphide and gold chloride without passing through the intermediate compound $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$, if instead of adding benzyl sulphide to gold chloride, the aqueous solution of the latter be poured cautiously, into a large excess of benzylsulphide in alcohol. First, the mixture became yellowish, but in 15-20 minutes, it became perfectly white. It was then filtered and washed with alcohol and ether. Herrmann observed that the compound, he prepared, when exposed to air, became yellowish. This was probably due to the presence of traces of $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ in the compound, as an impurity. For the pure compound that we obtained was very stable. It could be kept for months together without decomposition or any change of colour. The melting point given by Herrmann is 122° , whereas our compound melted at 125° . This also indicates the presence of impurities in his compound. (Found: Au, 44.11; Cl, 8.05. $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Au, 44.12; Cl, 7.95 per cent.)

